

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 46

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each psalm offers. Each psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 46

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 46:0 For the choir director. <i>A Psalm</i> of the sons of Korah, †set to Alamoth. A Song.</p>	<p>Psa. 46:1 עַל-עֲלָמוֹת שִׁיר : 2 אֱלֹהִים לָנוּ מִחֶסֶה וְעֹז עֲזָרָה בְּצָרוֹת נִמְצָא מֵאֵד : 3 עַל-כֵּן לֹא-יִירָא בְּהַמִּיר אֲרֶץ וּבְמוֹט הָרִים בְּלֵב יַמִּים : 4 יַהֲמוּ יַחְמְרוּ מִיָּמִיו יִרְעֵשׁוּ-הָרִים בְּגִאֲוֹתָו סֵלָה : 5 נָהָר פִּלְגָיו יִשְׁמְחוּ עִיר-אֱלֹהִים קָדַשׁ מִשְׁכְּנֵי עֲלִיֹן : 6 אֱלֹהִים בְּקִרְבָּהּ בַּל-תִּמּוֹט יַעֲזְרָה אֱלֹהִים לְפָנֹת בְּקָר : 7 הָמוּ גוֹיִם מָטוּ מִמְּלָכוֹת נָתַן בְּקוֹלוֹ תִּמּוֹג אֲרֶץ : 8 יִהְיֶה צְבָאוֹת עִמָּנוּ מִשָּׁגֵב-לָנוּ אֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב סֵלָה : 9 לְכוּ-יַחֲזוּ מִפְּעֻלוֹת יְהוָה אֲשֶׁר-שָׁם שִׁמּוֹת בְּאֲרֶץ : 10 מִשְׁבֵּית מַלְחָמוֹת עַד-קִצָּה הָאָרֶץ קִנְשֵׁת יִשְׁבֵּר וְקִצֵּץ תִּנְיֵת עֲגָלוֹת יִשְׂרָאֵל בְּאֵשׁ : 11 הִרְפוּ וְדַעוּ כִּי-אֲנֹכִי אֱלֹהִים אֲרוֹם בְּגוֹיִם אֲרוֹם בְּאֲרֶץ : 12 יִהְיֶה צְבָאוֹת עִמָּנוּ מִשָּׁגֵב-לָנוּ אֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב סֵלָה :</p>
<p>Psa. 46:1 God is our ^arefuge and strength,</p>	
<p>¹A very ^bpresent help ^cin ²trouble.</p>	
<p>² Therefore we will ^anot fear, though ^bthe Earth should change</p>	
<p>And though ^cthe mountains slip into the heart of the ¹sea;</p>	
<p>³ Though its ^awaters roar <i>and</i> foam, Though the mountains quake at its swelling pride. ¹Selah.</p>	
<p>Psa. 46:4 There is a ^ariver whose streams make glad the ^bcity of God, The holy ^cdwelling places of the Most High.</p>	
<p>⁵ God is ^ain the midst of her, she will not be moved;</p>	
<p>God will ^bhelp her ¹when morning dawns.</p>	
<p>⁶ The ¹nations ^amade an uproar, the kingdoms tottered;</p>	
<p>He ^{2b}raised His voice, the Earth ^cmelted.</p>	
<p>⁷ The LORD of hosts ^ais with us; The God of Jacob is ^bour stronghold. Selah.</p>	
<p>Psa. 46:8 Come, ^abehold the works of the LORD,</p>	
<p>¹Who has wrought ^bdesolations in the Earth.</p>	
<p>⁹ He ^amakes wars to cease to the end of the Earth;</p>	

<p>He ^bbreaks the bow and cuts the spear in two; He ^cburns the chariots with fire. ¹⁰ "1Cease <i>striving</i> and ^aknow that I am God; I will be ^bexalted among the ²nations, I will be exalted in the earth." ¹¹ The LORD of hosts is with us; The God of Jacob is our stronghold. Selah.</p>	
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References

Psalm 46:1

¹Or *Abundantly available for help*

²Or *tight places*

^aPs 14:6; 62:7, 8

^bDeut 4:7; Ps 145:18

^cPs 9:9

Psalm 46:2

¹Lit *seas*

^aPs 23:4; 27:1

^bPs 82:5

^cPs 18:7

Psalm 46:3

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 93:3, 4; Jer 5:22

Psalm 46:4

^aPs 36:8; 65:9; Is 8:6; Rev 22:1

^bPs 48:1; 87:3; 101:8; Is 60:14; Rev 3:12

^cPs 43:3

Psalm 46:5

¹Lit *at the turning of the morning*

^aDeut 23:14; Is 12:6; Ezek 43:7, 9; Hos 11:9; Joel 2:27; Zech 2:5

^bPs 37:40; Is 41:14; Luke 1:54

Psalm 46:6

¹Or *Gentiles*

²Lit *gave forth*

^aPs 2:1, 2

^bPs 18:13; 68:33; Jer 25:30; Joel 2:11; Amos 1:2

^cAmos 9:5; Mic 1:4; Nah 1:5

Psalm 46:7

^aNum 14:9; 2 Chr 13:12

^bPs 9:9; 48:3

Psalm 46:8

¹Or *Which He has wrought as desolations*

^aPs 66:5

^bIs 61:4; Jer 51:43

Psalm 46:9

^aIs 2:4; Mic 4:3

^b1 Sam 2:4; Ps 76:3

^cIs 9:5; Ezek 39:9

Psalm 46:10

¹Or *Let go, relax*

²Or *Gentiles*

^aPs 100:3

^bIs 2:11, 17

Targum

Psa. 46:1 For praise, by the sons of Korah, through the spirit of prophecy when their father was hidden from them, but they were saved, and they recited this song. ² God is for us security and strength; a help in distress we shall find indeed. ³ Because of this we will not be afraid in the time our fathers passed from the land, when the mountains totter in the depth of the great sea. ⁴ His waters shake, they become muddy from their dust; the mountains tremble in your pride forever. ⁵ Peoples like rivers and their fountains come and make glad the city of the LORD, and they pray in the LORD's sanctuary, his exalted dwelling. ⁶ The presence of the LORD is within it, it will not be shaken; the LORD will help her for the merit of Abraham who prayed on it at the morning hours. ⁷ When the Torah was given to his people, the Gentiles trembled; kingdoms shook when he raised his voice; and when he gave the Torah to his people, the inhabitants of the Earth melted. ⁸ The word of the LORD Sabaoth is our help; the God of Jacob is a stronghold for us forever. ⁹ Come, see the deeds of the LORD who has put devastation on the wicked of the land. ¹⁰ He annuls war to the ends of the Earth; he will break the bow and shatter the lance; the round shields he will burn with fire. ¹¹ Cease from war, and know that I am the LORD, exalted among the peoples, exalted over the inhabitants of the Earth. ¹² The word of the LORD Sabaoth is our help; the God of Jacob is a stronghold for us forever.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction and Superscript

This psalm was authored by the sons of Korach after their father disappeared before their eyes. The LORD delivered Korach's sons from the Earth, which opened up and threatened to swallow them with their father. The LORD delivered Korach's sons with divine salvation. The sons foresaw the future where Israel was threatened and damaged by foreign armies and by cataclysms.

The psalm's title alludes to the many worlds thus indicating that the LORD's salvation is expressed constantly throughout the world.

עֲלֵמוֹת שִׁיר (alamot sheer) – means "a song to the maiden." The phrase is an idiom meaning "the mysteries of life" which are hidden to most people but can be sensed in the ecstasy of song. *Alamot* was the name of a musical instrument that women played.

Israel owes its current and future good fortune to the LORD. This psalm is directed to the Sefirah Netzach.

To Him who grants victory, by the sons of Korach, upon the mysteries of son.

Verse one

Remember to place your full trust in the LORD for the present and the future.

God is our trust and strength, a ready helper in times of trouble.

Verse two

Israel would not fear what was happening on the Earth even when it is undergoing violent change. Why? Because Israel places its trust in the LORD to take care of them.

God is our trust and strength, a ready helper in times of trouble.

occurs, which moves mountains into the midst of the seas.

Verse three

Israel will not be afraid because she will see the LORD's hand in the midst of catastrophes. Meditate upon the verse.

Though its waters roar and foam, though the mountains quake at its swelling pride. Selah.

Verse four

Even in the violent changes of the Earth there will be one place where things will not be destroyed or damaged. That place is where the Temple was built, the city of Jerusalem.

There is one river; His streams they make glad the city of God, of Him Who is sanctified in the dwelling-places of the Host High.

Verse five

This is just a reminder that the LORD does not only dwell in the Temple in Jerusalem.

God is in this midst, He is everywhere, therefore do not waver. The LORD will help it at the dawn of morning.

Verses six & seven

Perhaps the pagan leaders of the world will see how the LORD affected history. These people may come to know the LORD as the world's leader. Meditate upon this sentence.

Though nations are in anxious tumult, though Kingdoms totter, through His call of thunder has decreed that the Earth shall melt.

The God of hosts is with us; the God of Jacob is our high tower. Selah.

Verse eight

How does the LORD is here? The answer is to look at everything on the Earth.

Come behold the works of the LORD, who made desolations on Earth.

Verse nine

The LORD desires that all wars stop. War destroys the beauty of the Earth.

The LORD makes wars cease until the end of the Earth; He breaks the box and cuts the spear to pieces; He burns the chariots of fire.

Verse ten

The LORD will destroy all the peoples who do worship idols and false gods.

"Detest and know that I am God, exalted among the nations, exalted upon Earth.

Verse eleven

What is our high tower? Ancient cities were built with high walls and a high tower so that lookouts could see if an enemy was approaching. Jerusalem had a tower named "David's tower." When the Assyrians and Babylonians came to the city, a guard in the tower would signal an alarm. Meditate upon this verse,

The LORD is with us; the God of Jacob is our high tower. Selah.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To Him who grants victory, by the sons of Korach, upon the mysteries of son.

God is our trust and strength, a ready helper in times of trouble.

Though its waters roar and foam, though the mountains quake at its swelling pride.

Selah.

God is in this midst, He is everywhere, therefore do not waver. The LORD will help it at the dawn of morning.

Though nations are in anxious tumult, though Kingdoms totter, through His call of thunder has decreed that the Earth shall melt.

The God of hosts is with us; the God of Jacob is our high tower. Selah.

Come behold the works of the LORD, who made desolations on Earth.

The LORD makes wars cease until the end of the Earth; He breaks the bow and cuts the spear to pieces; He burns the chariots of fire.

The LORD is with us; the God of Jacob is our high tower. Selah.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

